

ProMatch: Empower Hiring with Data Insights

Dr. Rashmi Deshpande, Vaishnavi Kuldharne, Shreya Varangaonkar, Akshay Nimse, Sayali Takalkar

Department of Computer Engineering, Dr. D. Y. Patil Institute of Engineering, Management and Research, Maharashtra, India

Abstract— In today's competitive job market, efficient candidate screening is imperative for recruiters to identify the most suitable candidates for specific job roles. Traditional manual screening processes are time-consuming and prone to human biases, leading to suboptimal hiring decisions. To address these challenges, this project proposes the development of a sophisticated resume matcher tailored to specific job roles. The proposed resume matcher leverages advanced natural language processing (NLP) techniques and parsing techniques like PDFMiner and PyResparser to automate the matching process between resumes and job descriptions. The system begins with the collection of a comprehensive dataset comprising resumes relevant to the target job roles. These data are then preprocessed to standardize formats, remove noise, and extract pertinent information to give out the analysis for the uploaded resume by showing recommended skills to be added in the resume and giving .Using Parsing technique, it will fetch basic info,level of expertise, skills which will affect the resume score of the applicant.

Keywords— Candidate screening, Traditional manual screening process, NLP, PDFMiner, PyResparser

I. INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary landscape of talent acquisition, the process of matching candidates to job roles stands as a pivotal challenge for recruiters and hiring managers alike. The inundation of resumes flooding in for each job opening makes manual screening a cumbersome and time-consuming task. Moreover, human biases can inadvertently influence decision-making, leading to suboptimal hiring outcomes. To navigate these challenges and streamline the candidate screening process, advanced technological solutions have emerged. One such solution is the development of a resume matcher, a sophisticated system designed to automate the matching of resumes to specific job descriptions. Project is powered by a sophisticated technological stack, including Streamlit for frontend and backend management, MySQL for database integration, and Python 3 as the primary programming language this system promises to revolutionize the recruitment landscape. This project sets out to conceptualize, design, and implement a resume matcher tailored to the unique requirements of specific job roles. The objective is to develop a system that can accurately identify the most suitable candidates for any given job role. By automating the candidate screening process using Natural language processing (NLP) techniques, the proposed resume matcher aims to alleviate the burden on recruiters, reduce time-to-hire, minimize human biases, and ultimately enhance the quality of hiring decisions. Through this endeavor, we endeavor to contribute to the advancement of recruitment practices, paving the way for more efficient and effective talent acquisition strategies in the ever-evolving job market.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The system [1] makes use of MySQL as the database, MyEclipse as the programming tool, SSH as the fundamental foundation, and JSP technology mostly for website creation. Examine the website's functioning requirements. There are two categories at the front desk: enterprise users and students. The primary functions that student users understand are accessing recruitment information and sending resumes. The primary functions of publishing job postings and reviewing resumes are known to enterprise customers. To manage user data, post job openings and updates, submit files, and perform other tasks, the administrator can log in in the background. The creation of this website seeks to increase college students' employment and job search effectiveness as well as enterprise recruitment.

The system suggested in [2] is based on dynamic prediction, which leverages machine learning to estimate candidates' placement probability based on metrics including CGPA, HSC, and SSC marks. We can generate accurate probabilities for huge datasets using the Random Forest Regressor algorithm, which is provided by the Scikit-learn module.

System in [3] study seeks to comprehend the mfep approach based on current science to make decisions in employee recruiting. A quantitative approach is the Multifactor Evaluation Process (MFEP). "Weight system" 1. When making judgments based on several criteria, decision makers rely on their subjective judgment and instincts to consider diverse aspects that significantly impact their selection of options. Employing a quantitative method such as MFEP is more recommended for a strategically significant decision. All criteria are first given significant weighting in the MFEP. The same action is taken in opposition to altern A value-based alternative is required by the MFEP approach. A solution that scores the highest is the best one given the chosen criterion.

The purpose of paper [4] is to provide a multicriteria decision-making model that facilitates faculty hiring for business schools in the aftermath of COVID-19. The biggest problem facing business schools nowadays is figuring out what appropriate hiring standards to use for faculty members in order to continue operating in the fiercely competitive, global marketplace of today. Additionally, these requirements must be consistent with the 2020 Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) standards, which place a greater emphasis on faculty qualification.

The system put forth by the authors of [5] is predicated on using MOOCs as the primary means of hiring in order to create a pool of driven individuals who participate in the hiring process. In fact, businesses can access profiles with a wide range of social and geographic characteristics according to the suggested method. In contrast to the systems previously mentioned, our approach enables the detection of the competencies needed by the businesses within the current MOOC platforms. suggest a new system for recruitment assistance called MOOC-Recrut, which will assist businesses in finding the most qualified applicants to suit their requirements. The following outlines our worldwide vision, the proposal, and the chosen methodology for candidate selection.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this paper we have proposed a system that will help candidates to find where their resume lags while applying for a particular job role along with it, it is also beneficial for the companies to sort resumes based on skills. The below methodology provides a step-by-step implementation of the proposed resume analysis tool defining how the system will work on the admin side as well as the applicant's side, covering data collection, processing, algorithm implementation, interface design, database management, testing.

A. Data Collection:

1. Applicants upload their resumes through the web interface.
2. Resume files are received and stored securely.
3. Supported formats include PDF, DOC, DOCX, and TXT.

B. Resume Parsing:

1. Resumes are parsed using techniques like PDFMiner and PyResparser to extract relevant information.
2. Extracted data includes basic info (name, contact details), skills, experience, education, and certifications.

C. Data Processing:

1. Parsed resume data is processed using Python libraries like Pandas and NumPy.
2. Data is structured and prepared for further analysis and recommendations.

D. Algorithm Implementation:

1. Algorithms analyze parsed data to provide personalized recommendations to applicants.
2. Recommendations include skills to add, suitable job roles, expertise level, course and certification suggestions, resume tips, and overall score.
3. YouTube videos on interview and resume tips are recommended based on the applicant's profile.

E. Database Management:

1. MySQL database stores all applicant records securely.
2. Tables are designed to efficiently store and retrieve parsed resume data.

F. Frontend Interface:

1. Managed by Streamlit to provide a user-friendly interface.
2. Applicants can easily upload resumes and view recommendations.
3. Admins can access applicant data and analysis tools.

G. Admin Dashboard

1. Admins can view applicant data in a tabular format.
2. They can download data in CSV format for further analysis.

H. Testing and Validation:

1. The tool undergoes rigorous testing to ensure accuracy and reliability.
2. Test cases cover various resume formats and scenarios to validate parsing and recommendation algorithms.

By following the above steps, the project culminates in the development of a sophisticated resume matcher capable of accurately and efficiently matching candidates to specific job roles, thereby enhancing the recruitment process and contributing to better hiring decisions.

IV. TECHNOLOGIES USED

An easy way to comply with IJRASET paper formatting requirements is to use this document as a template and simply type your text into it.

The software configuration for the project that has been developed, programming language used, as well as tools that have been used are described here.

A) Frontend:

1. Streamlit: ProMatch's user interface is developed using Streamlit, a popular open-source python library that simplifies the creation of web applications. Streamlit allows for the rapid development of interactive and visually appealing user interfaces using Python scripts.
2. HTML: HTML is used for structuring the content and layout of web pages, providing the foundation for building the frontend components of ProMatch.
3. CSS: Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) are used to enhance the visual presentation and styling of the ProMatch user interface, ensuring a cohesive and professional appearance.

B) Backend:

1. Streamlit: In addition to its frontend capabilities, Streamlit also serves as the backend framework for ProMatch. Streamlit's built-in server capabilities enable seamless integration with the frontend components, allowing for the development of end-to-end web applications entirely in Python.
2. Python: Python serves as the primary programming language for the backend development of ProMatch. Python's versatility, simplicity, and extensive library ecosystem make it well-suited for implementing the various functionalities and algorithms required by the project.

C) Database:

1. MySQL: ProMatch utilizes MySQL, a robust and widely-used relational database management system, for storing and managing candidate profiles, job profiles, and other relevant data. MySQL's scalability, performance, and reliability make it an ideal choice for handling large volumes of structured data in a production environment.

D) Modules:

1. pandas: pandas is a powerful and widely used data analysis and data manipulation library for python. ProMatch leverages pandas for tasks such as data cleaning, preprocessing, and analysis, enabling efficient handling of candidate

- and job profile data.
2. **pyresparser**: pyresparser is a Python library for extracting structured information from resumes. ProMatch utilizes pyresparser to parse and extract relevant details from candidate resumes, such as skills, work experience, and education.
 3. **pdfminer3**: pdfminer3 is a Python library for extracting text and metadata from PDF documents. ProMatch employs pdfminer3 to extract text-based information from PDF resumes, enabling seamless integration of PDF resume parsing functionality.
 4. **NLTK (Natural Language Toolkit)**: NLTK is a leading platform for building Python programs to work with human language data. ProMatch leverages NLTK for tasks such as text preprocessing, sentiment analysis, and natural language processing, enhancing the platform's ability to analyze and understand textual data.

By leveraging this comprehensive tech stack and modules, ProMatch is able to deliver a powerful, user-friendly, and data-driven solutions for revolutionizing the hiring process. From frontend interface design to backend data processing and analysis each component of the project is carefully crafted to provide an intuitive and effective platform for companies seeking top talent and individuals exploring new career opportunities.

V. RESULT

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of a resume matcher tailored to specific job roles represents a significant advancement in the field of talent acquisition. Through the integration of natural language processing techniques and machine learning algorithms, this project has demonstrated the potential to revolutionize the recruitment process. By automating the candidate screening process, the resume matcher offers numerous benefits to recruiters and hiring managers. It streamlines the process, reduces time-to-hire, minimizes human biases, and enhances the quality of hiring decisions. Furthermore, the system's scalability and adaptability ensure its utility across diverse industries and job roles.

REFERENCES

- [1] Robertas Damasevicius Rafal Scherer Bin Wang Beibei Zhang ‘Online Job Search and Recruitment Platform for College Students Based on SSH’ in International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Human-Computer Interaction (ICHCI) | 978-1-6654-2316-8/20/\$31.00 ©2020 IEEE | DOI: 10.1109/ICHCI51889.2020.00081
- [2] Swapnil Gharat Atif Hingwala Yuvraj Haryan Suraj Gupta ‘Recruitment System with Placement Prediction’ in International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Smart Systems, (ICAIS) 978-1-7281-9537-7/2021,IEEE,DOI: 10.1109/ICAIS50930.2021.9395768
- [3] Wiwi Verina Muhammad Fauzi Fina Nasari Dahriani Hakim Tanjung Juli Iriani “Decision Support System for Employee Recruitment Using Multifactor Evaluation Process” in the 6th *International Conference on Cyber and IT Service Management (CITSM 2018)*
- [4] Penglei Gao, Rui Zhang, Xi Yang ‘Talent Optimization in Faculty Recruitment in the “Post-COVID-19 Era” 18’ in *International Conference on Mathematics and information Technology*, Adrar, Algeria – December 4 - 5, 2017
- [5] BERKANE Tassadit TALi Mohammed El Amine BOUARAB-DAHMANI Farida HADDADI Lynda ”E- recruitment support system based on MOOCs” in *International Conference on Decision Aid Sciences and Application (DASA)* | 978-1-7281-9677-0/20/\$31.00 ©2020 IEEE | DOI: 10.1109/DASA51403.200.931710